

Literature Review on Effective Teaching Requires Structural Changes That Can Be Made by Academic Leaders

Nezir Ariz, Karaçalı Multi-Program Anatolian High School, Sur/Diyarbakır

Mehmet Akkuş, Bist Calligrapher Hamit Aytaç Secondary School, Kayapınar/Diyarbakır

Halit Çakmak, Karaçalı Multi-Program Anatolian High School, Sur/Diyarbakır

Mehmet Aktürk, Sultan Abdulhamid Han Anatolian High School, Ergani/Diyarbakır

**Rıdvan Çakar, Mehmet Aktürk, Sultan Abduhamid Han Anatolian High School,
Ergani/Diyarbakır**

Saliha Tanrıverdi, Bist Calligraphy Hamit Aytaç Secondary School, Kayapınar/Diyarbakır

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Abstract

In this study, it has been shown that a good teaching method helps students question their biases and motivates them to learn, by putting themselves in a situation where they see themselves as the authors of the answers and the agents of responsibility. However, when teachers can teach with this method, they face some obstacles and requirements. Some of these requirements are prerequisites for professors' behavior, and some are prerequisites for professors' perspectives. There are also some major barriers, some related to teachers' behavior and others to laws and regulations. Therefore, to have an effective teaching, faculty members of universities need to be aware of these barriers and needs as a way of increasing the quality of teaching. Effective teaching also requires structural changes that can only be brought about by academic leaders. These changes include hiring practices that recognize the importance of teaching ability, reward structures, quality assurance approaches that measure learning processes, outcomes in a much more complex way than routine methods and changing the way to achieve university accreditation. (“Effective Teaching Methods in Higher Education: Requirements and ...”) Nationally and locally recognized teachers are good leaders in providing enthusiastic educators with ideas, insights and best strategies for effective teaching in higher education. Finally, it is assumed that nationally and locally recognized teachers in higher education are more involved in the regulation of teaching rules. Therefore, curriculum planners and faculty members can improve their teaching methods. (“Effective Teaching Methods in Higher Education: Requirements and ...”) This is because of the correlation between the two findings. The teacher's ability to adapt and balance the use of a particular method is crucial, as the influence of the various methods is undoubtedly governed by differences at the student level. (“Reviews of Teaching Methods – What are the Fundamental Problems? | EERA”) This has been openly discussed in some of the reviews that formed the basis of this study. Our argument is based on analysis of all empirical material. The second choice will also involve the methodical and deliberate development of students' metacognitive abilities. Our

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research shows, first of all , that there is a distinction between students who are labeled as underperforming or who have been diagnosed with some form of learning disability, and those who do not have any of these labels or diagnoses when it comes to them.

Keywords: *Effective Teaching, Academic Leadership, Structural Changes in Education, Teaching Methods*

1. Introduction

According to our research, for example, constructivist teaching strategies such as exploration-based learning and problem-based learning have generally been found to be less effective for students with poor academic performance or diagnosed with a variety of learning (eg , Alfieri , Brooks, Aldrich , & Tenenbaum , 2011; Hmelo - Silver, 2004; Kirschner , Sweller and Clark, 2006). In many of the reviews of technology-related phenomena such as educational virtual reality, augmented reality, and computer simulation , it is clear that these are various potential conveniences for many students, but also potential risks for others. These can be divided into two categories:

- *facilities and*
- *risks*

When it comes to the use of technological artifacts in the classroom (in this case, augmented reality or AR), Wu , Lee, Chang, and Liang (2013) discuss the critical importance of teachers being sensitive to the various needs of their students. Students may experience cognitive overload in an AR learning environment due to the large amount of information they are exposed to, the multiple technological devices they must use, and the difficult tasks they must complete. In other words, students will need to be able to multitask to be successful in AR environments. Dunleavy et al. (2009) found that when students take part in a multi-user augmented reality simulation, they often experience feelings of being overwhelmed and confused, as the simulation requires them to deal with foreign technologies in addition to difficult tasks. In addition, the tasks that students are asked to complete in AR environments may require them to apply and synthesize various complex skills

such as mathematical estimation, collaborative problem solving, technology manipulation , and spatial navigation (Dunleavy et al., 2009).

Earlier studies have suggested that the lack of these core abilities is one of the factors contributing to the difficulties students face when trying to learn in AR environments (Kerawla et al., 2006; Klopfer & Squire , 2008; Squire & Jan 2007). Especially for younger students and those inexperienced in conducting open-ended research, added scaffolding and support will be needed to help students formulate a proper plan of action, seek workable solutions to their problems, and interpret the clues provided by technological devices. This will be necessary to help students create a proper action plan, look for workable solutions to their problems, and generate clues (Klopfer & Squire , 2008).

2. The Gap Between Research and Practice

role of the instructor is critical when it comes to coordinating the use of computer simulations with curriculum aims and students' needs . (Smetana & Bell, 2012, p. 1359) The research-practice distinction is the subject of the third overview finding. The gap between research and practice is a third issue discussed in several research reviews included . Still , despite the limitations described in the earlier paragraph and the impossibility of supplying ubiquitous "perfect" answers , it is possible to argue that research conducted over time has addressed the relative merits of certain teaching approaches. On the other hand, trainers do not always put strategies into practice, and the research-to-implementation gap is something that is problematized and explored in many of the included articles.

The fact that research on various teaching techniques is not done in real classrooms has been questioned in various assessments. In fact, much of the primary empirical research that is part of the reviews we review is conducted in laboratories whose contextual settings are in many ways quite different from typical classrooms. For example, this is what Duit and Treagust (2003) concluded in their review about conceptual development in scientific education:

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It seems that too many educators risk viewing educational research in general as unimportant. (Lijnse, 2000). For example, Kennedy (1997) has argued that the 'horrible reputation of educational research' (Kaestle, 1993) is related to the dominance of cognitive psychology in basic research. Kaestle (1993) said that educational research has a bad reputation.

This type of research is often conducted in controlled environments such as laboratories because it makes it easy to closely check all the factors involved. To achieve an elevated level of 'cleanliness' in an experiment, one must be willing to sacrifice the fact that the findings do not always contribute to real improvements in educational practice. Wright (1993) used similar reasons to explain why policymakers, curriculum architects, and science educators often view research on scientific education as unhelpful. In addition, he argues, most scientists who study scientific education have little interest in putting what is understood into practice.

Some have complex and interesting histories, others need players. In the context of current educational practices, the lack of opportunities for argumentative activities by young people is the main obstacle to the development of scientific discussion skills among the younger generation. If children are to be given more opportunities to buy these skills, a meaningful change will need to be made in the way scientific lessons are organized and conducted. As a result, these teachers lack confidence in their ability to successfully manage sessions devoted to classroom discussion and discussion. As a direct result of this, such actions rarely occur. Most of the findings focus on the extent to which empirical research is oriented towards real classrooms, as well as the potential for research not conducted in real classrooms to affect the work teachers do in complex practices. As an example, Frederiksen (1984), in his review of problem-solving teaching in the 1980s, concludes that researchers with different interests and approaches work separately from each other as well as from teachers and real classroom settings.

In a study of reading comprehension education in the 1990s, Dole and others came to the same conclusion, that future research should be more classroom-oriented, didactic, and specific. There is the statement by Duit and Treagust in the 2000s that "the price to pay for significant experimental 'cleaning' is that the findings often do not affect actual teaching and learning practice."

And finally, in a review of the application of computer simulations conducted in the 2010s, Rutten (2012) cites an earlier review in 1998 by de Jong and van Joolingen . In this review, the authors concluded that future research should explore the role computer simulations play in educational programs. Consequently, it is essential that teachers have situational awareness and the ability to predict or know what will work for whom, how, and under what circumstances. The technique undoubtedly needs the reflective teacher, and the reflective teacher undoubtedly needs the method. In line with the arguments previously presented by researchers from various fields , we believe it is necessary not only to consider regulatory factors, but also to explain and problematize the complexity of the context in a way that practitioners working in that context can understand . the field of education can evaluate the external and ecological validity of a study. This is the case because regulatory factors can have a significant impact on research results.

3. The Gap Between Research and Practice

Recognizing that there is a disconnect between research and practice is not a new phenomenon or unique to the field of teaching techniques research. We have shown that the gap can be attributed to factors at the teacher and context level on the one hand, and to the fact that primary research is almost natural, didactic and non- specific on the other. It is possible for a high degree of experimental cleanliness to supply high internal validity, as can be achieved in a laboratory setting; however, this may also limit the external or ecological validity of the results (Bernstein, 2018; Khorsan & Crawford, 2014). The failure of primary research to confirm why a particular teaching approach works in each setting has been highlighted as a source of the research-practice gap in several studies. This failure is a result of primary research not answering the question:

In addition, many reviews have self-critical aspects where they direct criticism to the secondary level of work. We would also like to discuss that the long-standing gap between research and practice is an issue that needs to be addressed in primary and secondary research. (“Reviews of teaching methods – which fundamental issues are identified?”)

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Gough et al., research reviews are necessary for a variety of reasons. They can help inform decisions about what types of added research might be most productive to undertake, thereby contributing to the establishment of a positive feedback loop. Researchers, policy makers and practitioners should ask "what do we know and how do we know?" They enable them to answer important questions such as "what more do we want to know and how can we know?" Investigations are especially important to understand what is known and what is not. The assessments we reviewed generally exercised an appropriate amount of caution in drawing conclusions based on what is already known.

In addition, they highlight knowledge gaps and suggest ways in which they can or should be addressed in further work. However, when looking at an example of a research review covering a period of forty years, it is seen that the same kind of issues and knowledge gaps come up repeatedly. This shows up when you analyze the reviews. The virtuous circle metaphor (2012), previously used by Gough et al., was chosen to emphasize the idea that one does not arrive at the same place, but that there is a continuous improvement in one's knowledge. The concept of research studies as an essential part in creating virtuous circles is based on the premise that the conclusions and objections drawn from studies are (at least in part) the starting point for new primary studies.

The primary level carries a significant amount of responsibility when it comes to developing knowledge of educational practice that is more applicable to specific settings. However, much of the blame also rests on circumstantial research and how it manages the conflicting demands of particularity and generalization; Discussed by Pawson (2006) and Pawson et al.

The authors believe a more realistic approach should be taken to understand "what works," and they recommend using a realistic inquiry paradigm in reviews. A different notion of causality serves as the basis for the model, which contrasts sharply with the approach used in more traditional studies. Applied to the field of teaching techniques, this means that one must understand not only the context of the link between teaching methods and student learning, but also the underlying processes that link the teaching method to its impact on student learning ability. It is necessary to make assumptions and research about these interrelationships. Considering that,

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"what's the use?" "Who will benefit under what conditions?" reframed. Additionally, Pawson and colleagues argue that the conceptualization of interventions as dynamic and complex systems-within-a-systems imposes a certain set of limits or criteria on a reviewer . To begin, a limit has been set on the amount of floor that can be covered in an exam.

It starts with positivist and scientific research environments and then goes to highlight the virtues and flaws of such traditions for educational research. It concludes with some implications for the future of educational research. A set of methodologies that can be loosely called interpretative, naturalistic, phenomenological, interactionist, and ethnographic are brought together as an alternative paradigm and analyzed for its strengths and weaknesses for educational research purposes.

critical theory as a paradigm in which educational research is conducted has been phenomenal, and its implications for the research initiative are addressed throughout this article in several diverse ways that resonate with curriculum research. This is reflected in discussions of research and evaluation, which discuss how evaluative educational research has become by nature. Indeed, critical theory links the conduct of educational research with politics and policy making, and this is reflected in the discussion of research and evaluation here. ("RESEARCH METHOD COHEN ok - YUMPU") Complexity theory, which originated in the natural sciences but is increasingly entering social science studies, is a more recent development that is becoming an emerging trend

4. Methodological Approaches Based on Science and Positivism

Both naturalistic and interpretive approaches are used here. Authors Hitchcock and Hughes (1995: 21) argue that ontological assumptions lead to epistemological assumptions; they argue that these in turn lead to methodological considerations, which in turn causes instrumentation and data collection problems. Our analysis borrows an important concept from these authors. This view takes research methods beyond just a technical exercise and understanding of the world; it is informed by how we see our world(s), what we accept understanding as, and what we see as

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purposes of understanding. This view extends research methods beyond simply viewing them as a technical exercise and as a matter of understanding the world. This chapter also recognizes that educational research, politics, and decision-making are inextricably intertwined, and draws attention to the politics of educational research and its implications for conducting research (e.g., moving away from "pure" research).

People have always been interested in mastering their environment and understanding the foundations behind the phenomena that their environment shows to their five senses. They set out to achieve these goals through a variety of methods, the most important of which are experience, reasoning and research. These can be divided into three main categories (Mouly 1978). However, these categories should be viewed as complementary and overlapping rather than independent and mutually exclusive. These features are most readily clear in the context of seeking answers to complex contemporary challenges. We rely heavily on experience and established norms of behavior when trying to find solutions to the challenges that arise in our daily lives. Despite their potential to illuminate the ultimate truth, it is important to keep in mind that these methods have some limitations. For example, the limits of human experience in the form of common sense understanding easily become known when compared to aspects of a scientific approach to problem solving.

The public bases them on fortuitous events and applies them carelessly and without question. When compelled to evaluate them, they do so selectively, typically choosing only evidence that matches their hunch and ignores what is against them. When they need to evaluate them, they choose evidence that is consistent with their hunch. In contrast, scientists form their hypotheses methodically and rigorously. Any hypothesis they put forward needs to be evaluated using empirical data for their explanation to have a solid foundation in the facts. There is also the idea of control, which is what distinguishes a layman's attitude to experience from a scientists. When trying to explain a phenomenon , ordinary people usually do not make any effort to control any external source of influence. On the other hand, scientists are highly aware of the variety of causes of a given event; therefore, they resort to specific methods and processes to isolate and evaluate the effect of one or more of the probable causes of the phenomenon.

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From the beginning of systematic thought to the Renaissance period, syllogism served as the basic building block of logical argumentation. After that, its usefulness decreased as it was no longer dependent on observation and experience; rather, it has become a purely mental exercise. This resulted in a decrease in the effectiveness of the technique. One of the effects of this was that authority replaced empirical evidence as the basis of evidence, and the more authority one referred to, the stronger the stance became. This was one of the consequences of what happened. Misuse of science's primary tool inevitably led to science becoming sterile. When Francis Bacon began to place an increasing emphasis on the observational basis of science in the 1600s, it was the beginning of an era that would lead to a meaningful change in the history of thought. He criticized the deductive reasoning model on the grounds that its key premises are often biased concepts, which inevitably biases the conclusions. Instead, he proposed inductive reasoning, in which examining a series of individual cases would lead to a hypothesis and eventually a generalization. He made these criticisms in response to criticism of the deductive reasoning model. Mouly (1978) states that Bacon's basic premise is that given enough data, even if one has no prior idea of the meaning or meaning of the data, a careful observer will still discover important relationships and reminds us of the existence of laws even in the absence of such an idea. The most important thing Francis Bacon did for science was to free it from the deadly grip of the logical method, whose misuse has stalled the progress of scientific knowledge. Thus, insisting that validation be based on empirical data, he has shifted the focus of scientists to the natural world to seek answers to the challenges facing humanity.

Rather than being seen as definitive means of evidence, logic and authority became the source of hypotheses about the world and the events taking place in it. In the end, Bacon's inductive technique was replaced by the inductive-deductive strategy, which took and mixed the elements of Aristotelian deduction and Baconian induction. In this case, the researcher engages in a process that involves oscillating between induction (going from observation to hypothesis) and deduction (going from hypothesis to inference) (Mouly 1978). Hypotheses are thoroughly evaluated, and necessary corrections are made.

Kerlinger (1970) supplied a definition for this concept that can be summarized as the methodical, controlled, empirical, and critical exploration of hypothetical claims about supposed connections between natural phenomena.

5. Two Different Perspectives on the Nature of Social Reality

The perspectives of social science we have just named reflect surprisingly diverse ways of looking at social reality and are based on similarly diverse methods of understanding it. We have just realized these perspectives because they are defined by us. Examining both the explicit and implied assumptions used to support these concepts of the social world can supply the most fruitful tools for approaching these ideas. The research conducted by Burrell and Morgan (1979), which cataloged four different sets of assumptions, forms the basis of our research. Discussions about methods as well as their relative benefits, drawbacks, strengths and weaknesses have been going on for many years (Savignon, 2007; Maghsoudi, 2016), but recently there has been a significant shift towards post-method perspectives.

A recent analysis of published research clearly shows that the environment in which teaching, and learning takes place is the most crucial factor in deciding the effectiveness of a method (Kumaravadivelu, 1994). This is often conducted by using questions to set up real language usage. In this way, observation of a classroom should supply examples of activities involving the teacher and the whole class, activities involving individual students, and work done by students individually. Another indicator of the extent to which students actively take part in actual communication is provided by the length of time devoted to each type of interaction. In addition to providing input in the form of actual texts, one of the features of using communicative and purposeful language is that students take part in the development of course content with the cooperation of the instructor. Therefore, unlike the teacher's contribution to the linguistic form, the ratio of the student's input to the overall course content is an indicator of the student's active participation in the content production process (Griffiths, 2011).

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The first type of questions, known as showcase questions, are questions that do not require students to engage in deep critical thinking, as their purpose is to evaluate students' memory or force them to repeat a specific answer. Responses to display queries are often limited to a single word or at most a few words, and as a result they do not serve any communication-related goals (Behnam and Pouriran , 2009).

Typically, there is only one answer that can be given in response to a viewing question. The second category consists of reference inquiries. These questions need candid answers from students, and it is not always the case that the instructor is aware of the answer in advance. Students are encouraged to give longer and more complex answers to reference questions that are exploratory in nature, forcing them to choose from a variety of possible or alternative solutions. The last category of questions is called clarification questions and includes questions that have neither reference nor image questions. Revealing questions, which Behnam and Pouriran (2009) refer to as "Socratic Questions," are asked to solicit input from students about content or to check students' current knowledge, both linguistically and topically. There is not always a single correct answer to uncovering questions; sometimes it's too much. However, it is important to keep in mind that not all inquiries have any communication value. It can be argued that reference and elicitation questions have a more positive effect in developing a communicative atmosphere for teaching and learning, compared to demonstration questions, which are repetitions of previously learned information.

6. Teaching Environment

The environment in which education and training takes place is inevitably the most essential element in deciding whether a strategy or technique will be successfully implemented. While there are other elements in the game, these are the ones that have the most impact (Griffiths, 2011). The importance of context even suggests that postmethodologies created by the context and the needs of groups of learners in various cultures can replace methods, depending on the influence of external variables . Within this framework, the student's function plays a key role in deciding the level of achievement that can be achieved using classroom procedures . Therefore, the teacher's

experience and professional status are not as important as the opportunities and opportunities offered by the institution, but as important as a wide variety of other environmental factors, especially learners and their dynamics, in the formation of the learning environment. Turkey is part of the growing circle along with other countries such as China, Japan, Egypt, Poland, Netherlands and Russia. As a result, Universal Journal of Educational Research 5(12A): 71-76, 2017 focuses on Turkey along with these other countries. This class focuses on both content and language input and is designed to raise students' awareness of academic genres and traditions using oral and written communicative tasks to provide language practice with the relevant topic. Although task-based, each teaching unit uses a communication strategy to provide students with the opportunity to use the language in an academic setting. As a result, it can be said that the academic environments in which all the students taking part in this research were conducted were comparable. The purpose of this research is to explore how the local environment, particularly the characteristics of the students taught, can have an impact on the application of certain CLT teaching concepts and strategies.

To achieve this aim, the study will be guided by the following questions:

- (a) Does the dynamic of students in the classroom have an impact on their interaction patterns?*
- b) Does the dynamics of the learners have an impact on the material created during the lesson?*
- c) Do learner dynamics influence the questioning behavior of the instructor?*

Professional competence is a personal training that decides the productivity of professional tasks. It consists of knowledge, skills and professionally important personal qualities, experiences and value orientations. Our understanding of professional competence is that it is a personal training. Competence differs from traditional concepts such as "knowledge", "talent", "talent" and "experience" by its integrative nature, which is decided by personal characteristics such as practical focus, and the ability to work in a wide variety of ways.

In this context, "competence" refers to the ability to successfully perform a task in each situation. Such a definition of professional competence requires significant changes in the pedagogical

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support of the university curriculum. (“(PDF) A Methodological Framework for Project-based Collaborative ...”) These changes should be made so that the curriculum is filled with teaching methods that can supply the necessary comprehensive outcome in the training of future specialists. It is certain that the well-established practices of the academic curriculum in universities (lecturing, explanation, practice, etc.) play a key role in the professional development process. However, once a complex phenomenon such as competence is set up, its limitations are felt much more intensely than in the past. As a result of this, we believe that modern education practices should give importance to the ability of the student to perform independent activities, to create self-learning environments, and to give experimental and applied education to the student. It allows the implementation of flexible educational programs in which the student can work at a comfortable pace, as well as a choice of action and an opportunity to take initiative .

Today we should talk about the use of interactive educational methods that stimulate interest in the profession; promoting the efficient acquisition of educational materials; set up behavioral patterns; to supply an elevated level of motivation , power, knowledge, team spirit and freedom of expression; and most importantly, it contributes to the complex competencies of future experts.

Education is a teaching strategy that can be used in any subject area and looks to build skills and knowledge in that subject through sequential tasks, activities or games. Using this approach, students can develop professional and proper behavioral skills in the performance of professional duties. This method also allows the instructor to provide the participants with incomplete information. One of the benefits of education is that it enables all students to take part in the education process. This is an advantage. Training can help prepare individuals for, among other things, professional communication and teamwork, as well as the fulfillment of organizational or supervisory responsibilities. The educational process usually consists of many stages. This stage paves the way for later activities by creating a democratic and comfortable environment. It can be done in any imaginable way and by any means. In the next activity, the instructor will share with the students what they expect and what they aim to achieve. This phase is an important part of the protocol for the first training class of any program. It encourages interaction between group members and the development of communication skills. Even if students are already familiar with each other, it is still necessary to practice it.

7. Deciding the Order in which the Training Will Take place

No matter how long the training session is, the instructor will always begin by explaining the training technique to the students before discussing or writing down their expectations. It is recommended that participants accept the training rules or create an "agreement" with the trainer so that they feel responsible for their training. Each student handles ensuring that the "agreement" is followed to the letter. One of the instructor's tasks is to evaluate the total amount of knowledge the class has. In most cases, this is conducted using a questionnaire or checklist with questions about the training topic. The survey results show the students' readiness and provide the instructor with information that can be used to rectify the gist and balance of the topics, change the instruction, and simplify the exercises. It is especially useful to give a second survey after the training is completed. When the results are compared, the instructor will be able to decide how much the students have improved their readiness, which is an important indicator of how well the education is delivered. This will help develop the desire to improve professional behavior and activity.

8. Conclusion

Education At this point in the process, the most important purpose of education is to put it into practice by setting up direct contact between the instructor and the students. There are two phases involved in this part of the training. The first is information, and it can start by answering questions on surveys that make you feel the most awkward. Additionally, primary course content is taught at this point using a variety of approaches , including but not limited to lectures, seminars, role playing, debates, and small group work . The second phase is more practice-oriented; It aims to help participants gain experience that they can use in the real world. This goal can be achieved using activities such as role-playing, dramatization, discussion, "brainstorming" and other types of interactive work. Options are decided by circumstances. Documenting the student's progress during the lesson, for example using photography, is a vital part of the program. These photos can

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be seen as a reminder of how the work is progressing at any point throughout the summary. Education is therefore an effective method for developing students' professional competence, as it creates an environment where students can feel safe and comfortable, and gives students the opportunity to practice, in general, the steps necessary for future professional activities. Education through the resolution of individual cases is what the case study technique entails. The trick to this approach consists of doing a thorough examination of a predicament as a group, finding a solution, and then publicly defending that answer. Students develop skills in collaboration, autonomous modeling of response, independent reasoning, and defending their views as they go through the process of evaluating cases.

The topic section provides a description of the scenario and gives students the opportunity to characterize all aspects of the scenario; the information section reflects the characteristics of the evidence on which the final decision is made ; and the methodical part for instructors identifies where the case fits into the general framework of the lesson, the assignments students have to complete, and the pedagogical support available to solve the scenario. Solving problems presented to students requires the application of a wide variety of analytical approaches, including problem-based, cause-effect, praxiological , axiological, situational, prognostic, and other types of predictive analysis . Below is a list of productive results that can be achieved because of students' actions as part of the method:

- 1) *Familiarity with the situation, its content and features.*
- 2) *main problems, factors and personalities that can act.*
- 3) *solution concepts.*
- 4) *analysis of the consequences of the decision ; and*
- 5) *best variant, prediction of outcomes, a sign of potential problems, mechanisms, prevention and solutions.*

There are two separate phases of the work a teacher does when using this approach. The first step involves creating the scenario, creating the questions to be analyzed and creating methodological software support materials that students will use in their individual work. The in-class activities that the instructor does while discussing the case are the second stage of the process. At this stage,

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the instructor gives introductory and closing speeches, organizes a discussion or presentation, promotes a business environment among the audience, and acknowledges the students' contribution in the analysis of the situation. Students exert a productive influence on the formation of their professional competence by examining and analyzing their work experience based on real-world situations. This enables students to comprehensively enrich the knowledge and skills that underpin the professional world. Peer feedback is a strategy based on information (both objective and honest feedback) gathered through the performance of activities linked to the acquisition of new skills and fulfillment of existing professional responsibilities. Everyone taking part in the event, including those who see, evaluate and comment, is on equal terms. Feedback can be provided after various activities such as debates, performances and educational assignments. The use of firsthand training, where students directly address professional challenges, brings with it incredible potential benefits and chances for the application of this technique. Such feedback can be supplied to aspiring educators, for example, after class, during added education and training activities, and the like. There seems to be a need for much more work in the literature on this subject if they supply objective feedback so that they can make educated decisions and develop the skills necessary to supply information.

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